

Identify the Benefits of Student and Teacher That Lead to the Summer Courses Effective at JUC

Dr. Tahir Iqbal, Dr. Gilbert M. Talaue & Kaumail Almayan

^{1,2,3} Business Administration Department, Jubail University College

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to ascertain the level of students' and teacher's satisfaction on summer semester in Jubail University College (JUC) Male Branch. This research was carried out by using survey questionnaire and documentary analysis. Descriptive method was used in this research to assess the summer courses in JUC. Level of teachers and students' satisfaction was analyzed using the aforementioned tools during the summer semester of academic Semester 363. The respondents were 90 students with different specializations program, and 10 teachers were also included in this study.

Keywords: Jubail University College, Summer Courses, Satisfaction Level, Teachers, and Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Summer semester is very important for students because they can get higher marks and it helps them to graduate in less time. On the other hand, it is very important for teachers since, if they are free during the summer, they can take advantage of that and can take summer courses to increase their experience and to get additional money [2].

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the level of satisfaction of summer courses of Jubail University College Male Branch students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

- What are the most important reasons that make students take summer courses?
- What are the key reasons that prevent teachers to take summer courses?
- What is the level of satisfaction of student and teacher about summer courses in JUC Male Branch?
- Registered courses and numbers of students at semester 363.
- Studying performance indicators in the summer semester for all courses at semester 363.

Assumptions

- The students are not fully satisfied with summer courses offered by JUC.
- The teachers are not fully satisfied with summer courses offered by JUC.

Scope and Delimitation

The main objective of this paper was to assess the satisfaction level of Jubail University College Male Branch's students about the summer courses in JUC. The study used different respondents from JUC from different levels of schooling and give background about the courses and performance during the summer semester 363. Lastly, based on findings recommendations will be provided to JUC to improve the summer courses.

The study is limited to students and teacher at JUC Male Branch for the second semester of the schooling year 2016-2017. Under the aforementioned semester, 90 students who belonged to different specialization courses participated in this study.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed to identify the satisfaction level of JUC-Male Branch Students in terms of summer courses provided by the College. Consequently, the study served as a guideline for JUC and other institutions for improving summer courses. Results of this study will contribute the following to the literature and JUC:

The results of this study will be a basis for improving summer courses in JUC. Students of Jubail University College. An effective and high-quality summer courses will be provided for them. An opportunity will be provided by this study to its researcher to explore their knowledge while this study can be used as a reference in future [9].

2. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the entire methodology of the paper has been presented ranging from research design to data collection tools. Similarly, in this section, the researcher has shown all the data analysis techniques used in the paper along with their justification.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive method which is used to describe a characteristic of population or phenomenon being studied; It does not answer questions about who, when and why characteristics [3].

Since the study is about the satisfaction of summer courses in JUC Male Branch students, descriptive research is the appropriate method. With the use survey questionnaire as a tool, the researchers surveyed the student and teachers in JUC. There were ninety (90) students in the said courses and 10 teachers; they were the respondents of the study.

Sources of Data

The primary source of data collection was surveyed questionnaire while the secondary data was collected from different documents. The total number of respondents was 100 based on 90 students and 10 teachers of JUC. Student belonged to the second semester of the schooling year 2016-2017. Under the aforementioned semester, 90 students with a different program of specializations and teachers participated in the study [1].

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The instrument for data collection to answer the problem is the questionnaire. The questionnaire is a data collection tool that is also considered as the most effective and efficient data collection tool because of its convenience and ease of access. The survey questionnaire was distributed to the students and teachers, and then it was collected and interpreted to answer the problem.

Tools for Data Analysis

The data which was collected from the questionnaire were tabulated in a tabular form to make it easy for readers of this study. Afterwards, researchers analyzed the same data and drew conclusions from it.

Slovin formula (1960) was used to compute the needed number of respondents [5].

The formula for the Slovin is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

Where:

n = number of samples

N = total population

e = error tolerance (0.05)

3. PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION, AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

In this section, the researcher presented the findings of data analysis which were obtained by applying data analysis tools on the collected data. Also, interpretations are made in this section. Tables and figures on the succeeding pages present the gathered data from the respondents, analysis, and interpretation [5].

Table 3.1: Profile of Respondents in Terms of Year Level

Year Level	Number of Students	Percentage
Freshmen	0	0%
Sophomore	18	21.3%
Junior	21	25.3%
Senior	42	53.4%
Total	81	100%

The table shows the number of respondents in each level in JUC Male Branch. In figure 3.1, the senior students are the majority of the respondents (53.4%). Junior students are 25.3% of respondents. The sophomore students are the third of them (24.3%). However, there are no freshmen students among the respondents participated in our study

Figure 3.1: Profile of Respondents in Terms of Year Level

Table 3.2: Profile of Respondents in Terms of their Major

Major	Number of Students	Percentage
Business Administration (BUS)	17	22.6%
Management Information System (MIS)	15	14.6%
Computer Science (CS)	10	13.4%
Civil Engineering (CE)	18	24%
Mechanical Engineering (ME)	21	25.4%

The table above presents the profile, or the status of Jubail University College students participated in the study in terms of their major or specialization. The table shows that Mechanical Engineering students are the majority of the respondents, making them 25.4%. 18 Civil Engineering students participated or 24%. Business Administration students are 22.6% among respondents. Management Information System students are 14.6% among respondents. Lastly, Computer Science students position 15.4% in the study. The purposes of this table to show that survey are distributed to different students from different majors.

Figure 3.2: Profile of Respondents in Terms of their Major

Table 3.3: Profile of Respondents in Terms of how many time they take summer course

Number of Time	Number of Students	Percentage
Never	10	9%
One Time	20	18%
Two Time	30	27%
Three or More	30	27%

Figure 3.3: Profile of Respondents in Terms of how many time they take a summer course.

Table 3.4: Profile of Respondents in Terms of type of courses

Subject	Number of Students	Percentage
General	10	11.1%
Major	50	55.6%

Both	30	33.3%
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The table above shows the type of courses do the students prefer to study in summer. The table shows that 11.1% prefer general courses to study in summer. 55.6% prefer major courses to study in summer. 33.3% prefer both courses to study in summer.

Table 3.5: Profile of Respondents in Terms of type of reasons

The reasons	Number of Students	Percentage
Increase the GPA	30	33.3%
Finished your degree earlier	40	44.4%
To decrease the number of hours in normal course	15	16.7%
Solving the problem of conflict between subjects	5	5.6%

The table above shows the real reasons that make students study in summer. The table shows that 33.3% they study in summer to increase their GPA. 44.4% they study in summer to finish their degree earlier. 16.7% they study in summer to decrease the number of hours in normal course. 5.6% they study in summer to solve the problem of conflict between subjects [7].

Table 3.6: Profile of Respondents in Terms of taking summer course before for Teachers

The Answer	Number of Teachers	Percentage
Yes	6	60%
No	4	40%

The table above shows the percentage of teachers who have taught in summer. The table shows that 60% of them have taught at summer. 40% of them haven't taught at summer.

Table 3.6: Profile of Respondents in Terms of planning to take summer course in the future

The Answer	Number of teachers	Percentage
Yes	7	70%
No	3	30%

The table above shows the percentage of teachers who are planning to teach at summer in the future. The table shows that 70% are planning to teach in summer in the future, 30% of them are not planning to teach at summer in the future. The table above shows the preferred time to teach in summer for teachers. The table shows that 80% are preferred to teach in summer in the morning. 20% of them are preferred to teach

at summer in the morning. No one of them is preferred to teach at night.

Table 3.8: Profile of Respondents in Terms of the number of courses would the teachers take at the summer

Number of course	Number of teachers	Percentage
Only one course	5	50%
Two courses	3	30%
Three courses	2	20%
More than three courses	0	0%

The table above shows the number of courses would the teachers teach in summer. The table shows that 50% are preferred to teach only one course at summer. 30% is preferred to teach two courses in summer. 20% are preferred to teach three courses in summer. And no one is preferred to teach more than 3 courses at summer.

Table 3.9: Profile of Respondents in Terms of the reasons that prevent teachers to take summer courses.

The Reasons	Number of Teachers	Percentage
The motivation is not enough	4	40%
You prefer to spend the summer with your family	4	40%
You don't mind to take summer course	2	20%

The table above shows the real reason that prevents teachers to teach in summer. The table shows that 40% said the motivation is not enough. 40% prefer to spend the summer with their family. 20% they don't mind to take a summer course.

The number of courses offered during the summer semester was 363 in All Departments 19 courses, Where he worked the Department of Business Administration has introduced compulsory departmental materials, the Business Administration has offered six Courses, Mechanical Engineering five courses, and the Department of General Studies five courses, and the following table is shown Courses offered in each department [8].

Table 3.10: Registered courses and student numbers.

Number of	Course Name	Dept. Name	Course Code
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students			
49	Calculus III	General Studies	MAT H 211
28	Industrial Psychology	Business Administration	BUS 283
15	Buyer Behavior	Business Administration	BUS 333
25	Organizational Behavior and Design	Business Administration	BUS 313
11	Strategic Management	Business Administration	BUS 411
14	Data Structures	Computer Science & Engineering	CS 205
27	Probability & Statistics	General Studies	MAT H 312
31	Engineering Hydrology I	Civil Engineering	CE 311
16	Hydraulic Engineering	Civil Engineering	CE 427
34	Engineering Economics	Business Administration	BUS 481
22	Machine Design I	Mechanical Engineering	ME 307
9	Systems Dynamics and Control	Mechanical Engineering	ME 314
12	Heat Transfer	Mechanical Engineering	ME 311
30	Applied Mathematics I	General Studies	MAT H 311
12	Applied Mathematics II	General Studies	MAT H 313
18	Fluid Power Systems	Mechanical Engineering	ME 423
26	Metallurgy	Mechanical Engineering	ME 428
28	Numerical Methods	General Studies	MAT H 314
28	Business Research Methods	Business Administration	BUS 321

The total number of students enrolled in the Summer Semester in the all Departments 477 students, these numbers varied during the semester, due to some withdrawal some of the courses are taught [6].

Student Achievement and Results: The following table shows student achievement in the courses offered in the semester 363, the number of students withdrawn is also calculated the average degree of students and the number of students who get DN. Where the study showed performance indicators a decline in the number of students registered with a final rate of 6%.

Average Degree	DN	Withdrawn	Number of students	Course Name	Course Code
73	0	6	49	Calculus III	MAT H 211
83	0	0	28	Industrial Psychology	BUS 283
85	0	0	15	Buyer Behavior	BUS 333
85	0	1	25	Organizational Behavior and Design	BUS 313
82	1	0	11	Strategic Management	BUS 411
71	0	0	14	Data Structures	CS 205
74	0	1	27	Probability & Statistics	MAT H 312
89	0	1	31	Engineering Hydrology I	CE 311
87	0	0	16	Hydraulic Engineering	CE 427
70	1	4	34	Engineering Economics	BUS 481
81	0	1	22	Machine Design I	ME 307
75	0	1	9	Systems Dynamics and Control	ME 314
81	0	0	12	Heat Transfer	ME 311
79	0	1	30	Applied Mathematics I	MAT H 311
68	0	0	12	Applied Mathematics II	MAT H 313
82	0	1	18	Fluid Power Systems	ME 423
83	0	0	26	Metallurgy	ME 428
77	0	1	28	Numerical Methods	MAT H 314
82	0	2	28	Business Research Methods	BUS 321

The most needed of summer courses

Based on findings, the most needed of a summer course in JUC is offering more courses for students since the most significant reason students take summer courses is to finish their degree earlier. And to offer more courses in summer, the

JUC should rise the motivation for teachers to teach in summer [4].

4. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section summarized the entire study and its results; conclusions were also made on the basis of this part since it showed the findings of the study.

Summary

This paper aimed to evaluate the level of students' satisfaction of summer courses in JUC Male Branch. Therefore, data were collected from Survey Questionnaire, and it was analyzed using descriptive methods and documentary analysis tools. With the help of aforementioned tools and techniques, the study described the level of satisfaction of e-services on JUC.

Conclusions

Based on the findings made the following conclusion were drawn:

It is analyzed that the JUC should offer more courses for students

It is revealed that the JUC should rise the motivation for teachers to teach in summer.

Recommendations

Based on the finding and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

It is recommended that JUC should offer more major courses in summer to fulfill the student's requirement.

JUC should increase the motivation of teachers to teach in summer

It is suggested that the classes should be in the morning for the convenience of students and teachers.

5. REFERENCES

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6 APPENDICES

Jubail University College كلية الجبيل الجامعية

Asalem Alikoum
we are a group of students from JUC BUS
Department, and we are making a research
relating to the effectiveness of summer courses
for students. We kindly ask you to fill the
survey to help us, Thank you.

Personal information

Name (optional):

In which level you are currently being
studying?

Freshman.
 Sophomore.
 Junior.
 Senior.

What is your major?

Business administration (BUS).
 Management information system (MIS) .
 Computer science (CS).
 Civil engineering (CE).
 Mechanical engineering (ME).

Summer courses information

How many time did you study at summer?

Never.
 One time.

Two times.
 Three or more.

Which subject do you prefer to study at
summer?

General subject.
 Major subject.
 Both.

How many hours do you prefer to take?

Three hours.
 Three to six.
 More than six hours.

What do you think the reasons for studying at
summer?

To increase the GPA.
 To finished your degree faster.
 To decrease the number of hours in normal
course.
 Solving the problem of conflict between
subjects.
 Others:.....